

A critical review of Vivekananda's educational thoughts for women education based on Neutrosophic logic

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Abstract

This paper presents a critical review of Vivekananda's educational thoughts for women education based on neutrosophic logic. Neutrosophic logic originated from neutrosophy, a new branch of philosophy. Neutrosophy studies the origin, nature and scope of neutralities as well as their interactions with different ideational spectra. Neutrosophic logic is the generalization of fuzzy logic and intuitionistic fuzzy logic. According to Neutrosophic logic, a proposition is $t\%$ true, $f\%$ false and $i\%$ indeterminate, where t, f, i are real values from the ranges T, F, I , with no restriction on T, F, I , or the sum $n = t + f + i$. Neutrosophic logic is a multiple valued logic that is capable of dealing with inconsistencies and paradoxes. Although Swami Vivekananda did not author a book on education, he reflected valuable thoughts on the subject that are very relevant and viable in the present educational system. Vivekananda clearly depicted the differences between women of India and USA depending on the difference of education. According to his views, women must be put in a position to solve their own problem in their own way. He believed that Indian women are capable of solving their own problems. He suggested that the Indian women must grow and develop in the footprints of Sita so that they would take up the vow of life-long virginity. He opined that Brahmacharinis set up centres for female education. Although he argued strongly for female education, some contradictions and paradoxes are found. These contradictions are critically discussed based on Neutrosophic logic.

1. Introduction

Numerous numbers of great persons were born in India. Among them Swami Vivekananda (Narendra Nath Datta, 1863- 1902), a great spiritual luminary, a great philosopher, educationist, religious leader, social reformer and great patriot-prophet is very influential son of India who contributed every sphere of education system of India. Recognizing his contribution, UNESCO (Kiran, 2008) acknowledged Swami Vevikananda as one of the eminent educationists of the world.

Swami Vivekananda did not author a book on education but he contributed valuable thoughts on the subject that are very relevant and viable in the present educational system. His thoughts on women education are compiled from his invited talk/lecture, conversation with people and his writings. He did not create any philosophy for education. His educational thoughts fully based on Vedanta philosophy and its interpretation. His thoughts for women education should be analyzed in the context of colonial rule and Indian tradition. His thoughts for women education created some contradictions and paradoxes. These facts are analyzed based on Neutrosophic logics.

2. Some basic concepts of neutrosophy and neutrosophic logic

Definition of infinitesimal number: A number p is said to infinitesimal if and only if for all positive integer N , the relation $|p| < 1/N$ holds.

In other words, an infinitesimal number can be informally defined as an infinitely small number.

Let $\varepsilon > 0$ be an infinitesimal small number.

Let us consider the non-standard finite numbers $(1^+) = 1 + \varepsilon$, where “1” is its standard part and “ ε ” its non-standard part, and $(^-0) = 0 - \varepsilon$, where “0” is its standard part and “ ε ” its non-standard part.

Definition of non-standard unit interval: $||^-0, 1^+||$ is defined as a non-standard unit interval where $^-0$ and 1^+ are analogously non-standard numbers infinitely small but less than 0 and infinitely small but greater than 1, belong to the non-standard unit interval respectively.

Neutrosophy: Neutrosophy is a new branch of philosophy. Florentin Smarandache went into folklore of philosophy and science when he introduced the concept of Neutrosophy in 1995.

Definition of Neutrosophy: According to Smarandache (Smarandache, 2005), Neutrosophy is a new branch of philosophy that studies the origin, nature, and scope of neutralities, as well as their interactions with different ideational spectra.

Etymology: Neutrosophy originated from French word *neuter* / Latin word *neuter* i.e. neutral, and Greek word *Sophia* i.e., skill/wisdom. Therefore, neutrosophy means knowledge of neutral thought.

Some Characteristics of Neutrosophy:

- It reveals that world is manifested with indeterminacy;
- It creates new philosophical theses, principles, laws, methods, formulas, movements;
- It attempts to interpret the un-interpretable;
- It criticizes old concepts, systems from many different angles;
- It demonstrates that in idea, which is true in a given referential system, may be false in another one, and vice versa;
- It attempts to bring peace in the war of ideas;
- It attempts to create war in the peaceful ideas;
- It attempts to measure the stability of unstable systems and instability of stable system;
- It is capable of dealing with paradoxes;
- It studies transdisciplinarity.
- It states that all is possible the even impossible too.
- It attempts to reveal that nothing is perfect, not even the perfect.
- It hypothesizes that no theory is exempted from paradoxes due to the language imprecision, metamorphic expression, various levels or meta-levels of comprehension/interpretation that might overlap.

Formalization: Suppose that neutrosophy considers a proposition, theory, event, concept, or entity denoted by $\langle \psi \rangle$.

$\langle \text{Anti-}\psi \rangle$ is defined as opposite of $\langle \psi \rangle$.

$\langle \text{Non-}\psi \rangle$ is defined as which is not $\langle \psi \rangle$.

" $\langle \text{Neut-}\psi \rangle$ is defined as which is neither $\langle \psi \rangle$ nor $\langle \text{Anti-}\psi \rangle$, i.e. neutrality in between two extremes.

$\langle \psi' \rangle$ is defined by any form of $\langle \psi \rangle$.

$\langle \text{Non-}\psi \rangle$ is different from $\langle \text{Anti-}\psi \rangle$.

It is to be noted that in many cases the borders between notions are vague, imprecise, it is possible that $\langle \psi \rangle, \langle \text{Anti-}\psi \rangle, \langle \text{Neut-}\psi \rangle, \langle \text{Anti-}\psi \rangle$ have common characteristics two by two.

Example:

If $\langle \psi \rangle = \text{man}$, then $\langle \text{Anti-}\psi \rangle = \text{woman}$ (opposite sex), but $\langle \text{Non-}\psi \rangle = \text{woman, trans-gendered person, trans-sexed person, hijra (fa'afafine), etc. (any person except man)}$, while $\langle \text{Neut-}\psi \rangle = \text{trans-gendered person, trans-sexed person, hijra (any colour, except man and woman)}$, and $\langle \psi' \rangle = \text{any type of man}$.

Fundamental Theory:

- Every idea $\langle \psi \rangle$ tends to be neutralized, diminished, balanced by $\langle \text{Non-}\psi \rangle$ ideas (not only $\langle \text{Anti-}\psi \rangle$ as Hegel asserted) - as a state of equilibrium.
- In between $\langle \psi \rangle$ and $\langle \text{Anti-}\psi \rangle$ there are infinitely many $\langle \text{Neut-}\psi \rangle$ ideas, which may balance $\langle \psi \rangle$ without necessarily $\langle \text{Anti-}\psi \rangle$ versions.
- To neuter an idea one must discover all its three components: Of sense (truth), of nonsense (falsity), and of undecidability (indeterminacy) - then reverse/combine them. Afterwards, the idea will be classified as neutrality.

Main Principle:

Between an idea $\langle \psi \rangle$ and its opposite $\langle \text{Anti-}\psi \rangle$, there exists a continuum-power spectrum of neutralities $\langle \text{Neut-}\psi \rangle$.

Fundamental Thesis:

Any idea $\langle X \rangle$ is T% true, I% indeterminate, and F% false, where T, I, F belong to subset of nonstandard unit interval $\|[-0, 1^+]$ and their sum is not restricted 100%, where $-0 = 0 - \varepsilon$, and $1^+ = 1 + \varepsilon$, $\varepsilon > 0$ are an infinitesimal numbers.

Definition of Neutrosophic logic: A logic in which each proposition is estimated to have the percentage of truth in a subset T, the percentage of indeterminacy in a subset I, and the falsity in a subset F, where T, I, and F are defined non-standard unit interval $\|[-0, 1^+]$, is called Neutrosophic logic.

Paradox: A paradox is a proposition, which is true and false in the same time.

A paradox cannot be presented by fuzzy logic but can be presented by Neutrosophic logic

Example: Philosopher's paradox:

Let Shri Sarkar be a philosopher who may not be characterized by his philosophical work.

- i) To be a philosopher, Shri Sarkar should have done some philosophical work and therefore Shri Sarkar should be characterized by that work.
- ii) The reverse judgment: if Shri Sarkar may not be characterized by his philosophical work, then Shri Sarkar is not a philosopher.

3. Vivekananda's Thoughts of Women Education

On the position of women in India Vivekananda's views on women are reflected from his numerous sermons, speeches, comments, conversations, writings, etc. He believed: "*Women are a power, only now it is for evil because man oppresses woman; she is the fox, but when she is no longer oppressed, she will become the lion.*" (Vivekananda -CW., Vol.5: 22).

Vivekananda opined that one could hardly find statements regarding incompetent for knowledge of women in the scriptures. His views on the deprivation of women in education include: "*In the period of degradation, when the priests made the other castes incompetent*

for the study of Vedas, they deprived the women also of all their rights. All nations have attained greatness by paying proper respect to the women. That country and that nation which do not respect women have never become great, nor will ever be in future. The principal reason why your race has so much degenerated is that you have no respect for these living images of Shakti.” (Vivekananda -CW, Vol.7, 215).

However, the position of women is degenerating in post independent India. One sorrow and important issue catches our attention of women harassment and rape cases. Women are more vulnerable to attack, because they are not taught how to protect themselves. If we look last five years data of “*National Crime Records Bureau*” (see Table1& Table 2), we get pathetic situation in India regarding increasing of rape cases (see Figure1) and total crime against women (See Figure 2.)

Table1. Rape case during 2007-2011in India.

Year	Rape cases against women
2007	20737
2008	21467
2009	21397
2010	22172
2011	24206

Figure1. Rape cases against women during 2007-2011in India.

Table2. Crime against women during 2007-2011in India.

Year	Crime against women
2007	185312
2008	195856
2009	203804
2010	2,13,585
2011	2,28,650

Figure2. Crime against women during 2007-2011in India.

Vivekananda seemed very enthusiastic in illustrating the privileged history of Indian women in the Vedic period where they enriched with intellectual power and spiritual knowledge. They enjoyed a substantial and significant status in the society in terms of their dignity, freedom, individuality. The idea of this type of equality he obtained from Vedanta philosophy (Rolland, 2010) which states “*the soul has neither sex, nor caste nor imperfection.*” Thus he created a paradox which is stated below.

Paradox: Is the Vedic period the golden period for women’s education?

- i) According to Vevikananda, Vedic period is the golden period because like Gargi, Lilabati, Khana and others are important women for Vedic education.
- ii) If Vedic period is the golden period, then why only few women names are found in the literature of education.

Vivekananda meticulously includes all those studies that are necessary for the all-around development of the body, mind and soul of the individual. For formal education, he proposed different curriculum for women.

Curriculum for women education:

- History and Purānas
- Housekeeping
- Arts
- Duties of home life
- Principles that make for the development of an ideal character
- Sewing, culinary art, rules for domestic works
- Uplifting of children
- Japa, worship, meditation,
- Self defense
- Religion, arts, science, housekeeping, cooking, hygiene-simple essential points in these subjects
- Morality and spirituality

Although he suggested above curricula for women he did not oppose higher education on the European lines. He praised University of Calcutta for opening doors to women for higher education before Cambridge University, Yale University, Oxford University.

Now the contradiction arises, he believes that the soul has neither sex, nor caste, nor imperfection. Every human being possesses a soul. Then why did he prescribe different curriculums for man and women? This implies that Vivekannada contradicts himself. According the principle of neutrosophy, contradiction arises due to considering contexts in a particular environment.

Soul Paradox: Does Vivekananda believe in same soul of man and woman?

- i. If Vivekananda believes same soul for man and woman, then he does not prescribe different curricula for man and woman.
- ii. If he prescribes different curricula for man and woman, then he does not believe that soul of man and woman are same.

Thus Vivekananda created the 'soul' paradox. In other words, he used this paradox to fulfill his education thoughts for women in that colonial period of India in order to uplift women.

He opined that ideal characters such as Sita, Savitri, Damayanti, Lilavati, Khana must always be presented before girls to imbue them with a devotion to high principles of selflessness. He laid emphasis more on morality and spirituality for women that of intellectuality. This also leads the contradiction to the fact that problem solving ability depends on intellectuality. If women are to solve their own problems as he suggested, intellectuality cannot be compromised.

He mentioned that the child of ideal mothers would make further progress in India. Great men are born in the homes of educated and pious mothers. He lamented that Indians reduced their women to something like manufacturing machines. He opined that the uplift of women, the awakening of the masses must come first, and then only can any real good come about for India. The duty of teaching in school ought to devolve in every respect on educated widows and 'Brahmcharinis'. He said, "*It is good to avoid in this country any association of men with women's schools*". Disassociation with men, is all round development of woman is possible? Here also contradiction arises.

He mentioned that educated women /celibate nuns will in time be the teachers and preachers of the Math. According to Vivekananda, they will set up centers and strive for the spread of female education. According to him, women must be given education and left to themselves. After having education, they will act as they think best. It implies that Vivekananda had faith in women. Vivekananda asked to all open girls' schools in every village in order to uplift them. He prescribed English and Sanskrit for widowed women in some cases. He highly praised educated and cultured American Women for their pure heart. American women are free and they control social and civic duties. They are free as birds. Few women marry before the age of twenty or twenty-five. They do all kinds of work. Comparing with them, he suggested that women should be educated with as much care and attention as the sons'. He prescribed Brahmacharya for both men and women. He opined that India would remain as backward if she cannot better the condition of Indian women. However, he criticized educated Indian women for taking Western modes of living. Here also contradiction arises, because he does not want to see same life style of Indian women like American women.

Why did contradictions and paradoxes arise in Vivekananda's thoughts? The answer lies in the fact that Vivekananda believed in Upanishada and Vedanta. Vivekananda recalled the paradoxical answer of the Upanishada to the question they propounded. The questions [Rolland, 2010] are: *What is the Universe? From what does it arise? Into what does it go?* The answer is: *"In freedom it rises, in freedom it rests, and into freedom it melts away"*. For Maya also, we observe Neutrosophic elements. Maya cannot be defined as non-existence any more that it can be defined as existence. It is an intermediate form between the equally absolute Being and Non-Being. Therefore, we see that the concept of using contradictions and paradoxes, he synthesized from Upanishadas and Vedanta philosophy and he applied it when it required. Before the inception of neutrosophy, he used some concepts of Neutrosophic idea to deal with complex Indian social and education systems.

4. Conclusions

We observed that the paradoxes were well basis of Vedanta philosophy and Vivekananda was a masterpiece of it. The contradictions of Vivekananda's thoughts on women education occurred due to his lectures in different times and different contexts, which is acceptable (sense) in particular culture but unacceptable (non-sense) in other culture. He always tried to improvise Indian women to set Sita and others as examples of ideal women characters. Basically he prescribed education for women first, and then let them decide what they want to do. He believed that Indian women can solve their own problems. The attacks on women catch our attention at regular basis that can be solved by the self defence mechanism of women. Self-defense for women is very relevant at present and Vivekananda prescribed it clearly (Vivekananda -CW.5.342).

There have been many changes in the field of education as well as in society. With the rapid progress of science and technology the whole world became very accessible through internet and other media. Ideas, thoughts, new inventions are quickly delivered to the peoples. Old ideas are interpreted with help of new theories or ideas. Thoughts of Vivekananda on education ought to be seriously re-examined at present and should introduce those parts which are relevant and applicable in order to achieve his cherished dreams of great India and Indian civilization.

It is generally accepted that Vivekananda's influence still working significantly. He was a dynamic personality with immense foresight. Based on Neutrosophy, it can be imagined that his thought on women education would change in order to meet the current needs of the nation. So it is the duty of the State to design the correct educational policy to women

education so that it would produce fruitful education for national and international development.

5. References

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